

An Analysis of the Principal's Managerial Role in Improving Teacher Performance at Muhammadiyah 8 Junior High School, Batu

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ABSTRACT

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This study investigates the role of the principal in improving teacher performance at SMP Muhammadiyah 8 Batu. The principal has a strategic responsibility to manage human resources and create a good working environment to improve the quality of education. Data were collected through observation, interviews, and documentation from the principal and teachers through a descriptive qualitative approach. The results showed that the principal carries out five main managerial functions: planning, organizing, directing, coordinating, and supervising. Planning involves establishing the school's vision and work program, organizing includes dividing tasks and strengthening collaboration between teachers, and directing is done through motivation, coaching, and training. Coordination is done to integrate the roles of all parties. Meanwhile, supervision concentrates on assessing teacher performance through periodic supervision. This study shows that principals who receive ongoing training to improve the quality of education can improve their teacher performance, especially when they can carry out their duties efficiently, especially in terms of motivation, professional coaching, and improving work culture.

KEYWORDS:

Principal managerial, Teacher performance, educational leadership, SMP Muhammadiyah 8 Batu

1. INTRODUCTION

Education is a fundamental factor in a nation's development. The success of an education system is determined not only by the curriculum and infrastructure, but also by the managerial role of the principal as the leader of the educational institution. In a global context, various studies show that the quality of education is greatly influenced by effective principal leadership oriented towards improving teacher professionalism^{1,2}. Principals with high managerial skills are able to optimally manage school resources, create a conducive work climate, and improve teacher motivation and performance in the learning process.

In Indonesia, the government, through Minister of National Education Regulation No. 13 of 2007³, emphasizes that school principals must possess five core competencies, one of which is managerial competency. This competency encompasses the ability to develop plans, organize resources,

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implement school programs, and supervise educational activities. These managerial functions serve as the foundation for principals in achieving national education goals, namely improving the quality of graduates and the professionalism of educators. However, in practice, not all principals are able to carry out managerial functions effectively and in an integrated manner with improving teacher performance.

Based on initial observations at SMP Muhammadiyah 08 Batu, it was found that the implementation of the principal's managerial functions still faces several obstacles. For example, in the planning aspect, some teachers are not actively involved in the development of the school's work program. In organizing, the division of tasks is sometimes not accompanied by consistent monitoring. Furthermore, academic supervision activities have not been running optimally due to the principal's limited time and the school's busy schedule. This condition has impacted the variation in teacher performance levels, particularly in lesson planning, media use, and implementation of student learning evaluations. On the other hand, the principal has demonstrated a strong commitment to improving the school's management system by increasing teacher collaboration and participation in all school programs.

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Several previous studies, such as those conducted by ^{4,5,6}, have shown that the principal's managerial role has a positive influence on improving teacher performance. However, most of these studies only focus on one or two managerial functions, such as supervision or organization, without examining the integration between the four main functions (planning, organizing, implementing, and supervising) comprehensively. Furthermore, research focusing on the context of Muhammadiyah-based private schools, particularly in Batu City, is still limited. Muhammadiyah schools have their own characteristics that emphasize the integration of Islamic values and modern management in educational delivery.

Based on this, there is a research gap in the comprehensive and contextual study of the principal's managerial role in modern Islamic educational institutions. This study offers a novel analytical approach, namely, an in-depth examination of the implementation of the four principal managerial functions within a unified system and identifying supporting and inhibiting factors based on empirical data from observations, interviews, and documentation at SMP Muhammadiyah 08 Batu.

The purpose of this study is to analyze the principal's managerial role in improving teacher performance, encompassing four main aspects planning, organizing, implementing, and supervising and to identify supporting and inhibiting factors in its implementation. Through this research, it is hoped that a comprehensive picture will be obtained of how principals can play a strategic role in developing professional and productive teacher performance. The urgency of this research lies in its contribution to improving the quality of school management and teacher development. The findings are expected to serve as a practical reference for Muhammadiyah and other school principals in optimizing managerial functions to improve teacher performance. Furthermore, the findings can provide input for educational institutions and policymakers in designing more effective school leadership development programs that align with the characteristics of Islamic educational institutions in Indonesia.

Located in the heart of Batu city is Muhammadiyah 8 Junior High School. This city is known for its abundant educational potential and a supportive learning environment. Muhammadiyah 8 Junior High School Batu is part of a network of Muhammadiyah schools strongly committed to student character and academic development. With adequate facilities and experienced teachers, the school strives to create an innovative and conducive learning environment. The local context, rich in culture and religious values, also adds a unique touch to the educational process at this school. Furthermore, the presence of an active community and support from parents are crucial factors in improving the quality of education, making Muhammadiyah 8 Junior High School Batu a significant educational institution contributing

significantly to the development of human resources in the area.

The choice of SMP Muhammadiyah 8 Batu as the research location was based on the school's strong reputation for educational management and human resource development. In such a situation, the principal's managerial role is crucial for improving teacher performance. Consequently, the quality of education provided to students will improve.

Junior high school teachers play a crucial role in building the foundation of students' knowledge and character during the transition from childhood to adolescence. At this stage, students experience various psychological and social changes that require an appropriate pedagogical approach from a teacher. Therefore, the performance of junior high school teachers is crucial to the success of the learning process and the achievement of National Education goals. Teacher performance is the action taken to carry out, complete tasks, and commit to achieving established goals and expectations. The word "performance" has the following meanings: "achievement," "show," and "execution of tasks" according to ⁷.

Teacher performance is closely related to the teacher's activities in carrying out their functions. An effective teacher is: 1) Cooperative personality, attractive appearance, great interest, consideration, and leadership, 2) Mastering good teaching methods, 3) having good behavior when teaching, 4) mastering various competencies in teaching⁸. Teachers as professional educators have a good image in society if they can show the community that they are worthy of being role models or examples for the surrounding community. The community will especially see how the teacher's attitude and actions are on a daily basis, whether there is anything worthy of emulation or not. Although all teacher behavior is always observed by the community, what must be considered is the teacher's attitude related to their profession ^{9,10}.

Teacher competence does not directly impact student achievement, but teacher performance significantly impacts student achievement. Teachers are expected to be responsible for their profession, not merely carrying out tasks without regard for results. Students' roles are also essential in supporting teaching and learning activities. Good collaboration between teachers and students will lead to satisfactory learning outcomes ¹¹.

Motivation, both internal and external, significantly impacts a teacher's performance. Internal motivation originates from within the teacher, while external motivation originates from outside sources. However, the success and progress of an educational institution depend not solely on teachers; the principal's role as a school leader also significantly impacts the success of an educational institution ¹².

Many studies on principal leadership have been conducted in general contexts, particularly in public schools with more established organizational structures and systemic support ¹³. However, research specifically examining the managerial

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role of principals in Islamic-based private schools, such as Muhammadiyah schools, is still limited. Private schools have different dynamics in terms of teacher development, resource availability, and the relationship between religious vision and educational management ¹⁴.

In the study entitled "Analysis of the Principal's Managerial Role in Improving Teacher Performance at SMP Muhammadiyah 8 Batu", the philosophy of ontology, epistemology, and axiology is studied. This study provides a deep understanding of the complex role played by the principal. Epistemology emphasizes the importance of appropriate research methods to explore relevant knowledge, while ontology shows that this role involves important social and emotional dimensions. This study is expected to make a significant contribution to the development of principal management practices and the improvement of teacher performance at SMP Muhammadiyah 8 Batu by understanding the values underlying educational practices, which can affect teacher performance and student learning outcomes. This will result in an increase in the quality of education, which is the main goal for all educational institutions.

This study aims to address this gap by examining in-depth how the principal at SMP Muhammadiyah 8 Batu carries out his managerial role in improving teacher performance, including aspects of motivation, professionalism, and work collaboration. However, previous studies have tended to overlook the dimensions of interpersonal communication and local organizational culture, despite their crucial role in leadership effectiveness ¹⁵.

Thus, this research presents novelties through a contextual approach based on local values, a managerial approach based on Islamic character, and the integration of collaborative dimensions in improving teacher performance. The results of this study are expected to not only add to the scientific literature in the field of educational management but also provide practical contributions for private schools seeking to develop more relevant and effective leadership styles.

This research is expected to provide in-depth insights into the role of principal management and its impact on teacher performance. Furthermore, this research is expected to make a positive contribution to educational development within the school environment.

II. METHODOLOGY

This study uses a qualitative approach to describe and understand in-depth the principal's managerial role in improving teacher performance at SMP Muhammadiyah 8 Batu. This approach was chosen because it captures social phenomena and leadership behaviors in a natural context and allows researchers to explore the subjective meanings of informants. A qualitative approach is relevant when the research focus lies on social processes, interactions, and dynamics that cannot be explained by numbers or statistics

alone. This aligns with the opinion of Scholars (2021) who stated that qualitative research produces findings that cannot be obtained through statistical procedures or other quantitative methods.

This research is descriptive, aiming to describe events and facts as they exist, particularly those related to the principal's managerial practices and their impact on teacher performance. This research design allows researchers to construct a factual picture based on observations and direct experiences in the field. The research location is Muhammadiyah 8 Batu Junior High School, which is geographically located in the center of Batu City and has the characteristics of an Islamic-based private school that is active in developing human resources and the school's organizational culture. This school was chosen because it demonstrates a strong commitment to educational management, but on the other hand still faces challenges in improving teacher performance evenly.

III. RESULTS

The Principal's Managerial Role in Planning, Organizing, Implementing, and Supervising to Improve Teacher Performance at SMP Muhammadiyah 08 Batu

1. Planning

The principal's role as manager is to manage the school. The management carried out by the principal of Harapan Ummat Superior High School includes planning, organizing, implementing, and evaluating as follows: (a) planning is carried out in advance with the structural team to formulate and determine the program, costs, and timeframe for the coming year; (b) the principal holds a meeting with the structural team and the foundation to seek approval, as the school is under the auspices of an Islamic boarding school; (c) the principal holds a meeting with teachers to socialize the program to be implemented for the coming year and to assign tasks to each teacher. The principal organizes by dividing tasks, assigning responsibilities, and assigning the structural team. The implementation stage involves the principal implementing the plan approved by the foundation, guided by the annual School Activity and Budget Plan (RKAS) and the general educational calendar ¹⁶.

In the planning management system, first, the principal and his team have compiled various school program plans to support a culture of quality within the school environment, which include: the formulation of the school's vision, mission, and objectives. Likewise, various School Work Plans (RKS) have been compiled with the resulting programs including the principal's short-term and long-term work programs, monitoring and evaluation programs, supervision, administration, curriculum, students, public relations, infrastructure, library, PPK, and literacy ¹⁷.

The principal has fulfilled his responsibilities as a school leader through his performance, primarily in improving the quality of the school's teaching staff. This includes

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empowering teaching staff through programs such as in-house training, which serves as a means for teaching and administrative staff to improve their competencies. Furthermore, the principal has empowered each teaching staff member to develop themselves through MGMP (Student Leadership Group), education and training, seminars, and entrepreneurship. The principal has carried out his role in accordance with the law governing the duties and functions of the principal¹⁸.

Planning management is a key aspect in principal leadership. The principal has a very important role in an educational institution. This study aims to determine the programs offered by the principal in improving the skills and planning of the principal in developing teacher productivity. This study uses a quantitative research method in the form of frequency distribution. The results of this study are: ideal learning planning based on the applicable curriculum requirements at Mts Anwarul Hasaniyyah school is included in the good category, the right strategy in developing learning programs applicable at Mts Anwarul Hasaniyyah school is included in the good category, problems and challenges in educational planning applicable at Mts Anwarul Hasaniyyah school are included in the moderate or sufficient category¹⁹.

2. Organizing

Organizing involves establishing the school's organizational structure, the school committee structure, and organizing all areas within the school, including student affairs, facilities, infrastructure, and curriculum. A principal's leadership within the institution they lead must motivate all school components to develop the school in accordance with the demands of current developments. Communication and socialization of school programs are also crucial for the principal to produce a quality school that meets community expectations²⁰.

In developing an understanding of quality, the principal's role as a manager is to plan, organize all types of activities, and implement the plans to be achieved. The principal, as a leader in the institution, must be able to direct, build togetherness, realize the school's vision and mission to advance the school, and have a strong determination to change the institution towards a better direction, namely the realization of a quality school^{21 21}. The principal's leadership role in the school organization is very important because the principal's strategic role also influences teacher performance in implementing the Teaching and Learning Process (PBM) activities. As an educational leader, the principal has quite heavy duties and responsibilities. The effectiveness of the principal in implementing management functions is the accuracy of the principal's ability to plan, organize, mobilize and control, and optimally utilize all educational resources, including personnel, funds, facilities and infrastructure, including information. This shows the extent to which the principal carries out his main duties properly and correctly to achieve goals²².

The management ability of high school principals in improving teacher performance at Attaufiq High School, Jambi City can be seen from the aspects of Planning, organizing, Implementing, Supervising and evaluating that have been made by the principal, the results are quite good. The management of high school principals in improving teacher performance has been implemented according to plan, although not yet fully as expected. The obstacle in improving teacher performance at Attaufiq High School, Jambi City is the lack of teacher awareness in improving the performance that has been evaluated. The strategy carried out by high school principals in improving teacher performance at Attaufiq High School, Jambi City can be seen from the aspects of planning, organizing, implementing and supervising the high school principal in improving teacher performance at Attaufiq High School, Jambi City, namely through the strategy of high school principals in binding teacher performance is by providing motivation, providing good examples, providing work that is in accordance with the teacher's educational background²³.

The principal's role as a manager is to manage the school. Management carried out by the principal of SMA Unggulan Harapan Ummat includes planning, organizing, implementing, and evaluating as follows: (a) planning is carried out with the structural team first to formulate and determine the program, costs, and time used for the next year¹⁶. In organizing carried out by the principal, it is to make all stakeholders into one excellent forum. Then, in the implementation, the principal carries out maximum mobilization and creates a forum to continue working together in implementing and developing the school's vision, mission, and goals. Meanwhile, from the supervision, the principal carries out evaluation activities and assesses all school programs, the performance of teaching staff and other employee staff²⁴.

3. Implementation (Actuating)

The principal, as the highest-ranking official in the school's organizational structure, naturally has significant influence in determining the direction of policies aimed at improving school competency in the classroom. The principal's presence is crucial because he or she serves as a motivating force for school resources, particularly instructors, staff, and students. Academic supervision is one of the principal's primary duties and responsibilities²⁵.

To enable teachers to carry out their noble responsibilities at school, they need to receive ongoing refreshment in the form of technical assistance. This technical assistance is provided to teachers as an effort to continuously increase their capacity. This assistance takes the form of academic supervision carried out by the principal and school supervisor. The principal is one of the educational components that influences teacher performance. Among the various factors that determine teacher performance at school is the principal's involvement in terms of leadership skills²⁶.

4. Supervision (Controlling)

Supervision is an activity that seeks to ensure implementation proceeds according to plan and ensures that organizational goals are achieved. If deviations occur, the source of these deviations is identified and what actions are necessary to address them²⁷. The principal's managerial skills and school climate influence school quality. Principals can take solutions, including making controlling activities a routine agenda, involving supervisors in these routine activities, and disseminating the results of supervision activities to teachers as a basis for improvement²⁸.

As a motivator, the principal must have the right strategy to motivate educators in carrying out their various duties and functions. This motivation can be fostered through managing the physical environment, managing the work atmosphere, discipline, encouragement, effective rewards, and providing various learning resources²⁹. A teacher's performance is greatly influenced by the role of the principal. Educational success does not solely depend on teachers. Educational success is also influenced by the principal's presence as a leader within a school. The principal at SDIT Buah Hati has not optimally implemented managerial principles. Therefore, the principal's role in improving teacher performance is needed, namely through POAC (Planning, Organizing, Actuating, and Controlling). The principal establishes goals together with teachers, staff, and the school committee through meetings to prepare the School Activity and Budget Plan (RKAS)²⁸.

Supervision plays a crucial role in efforts to improve the quality of learning at the elementary school level. Through planned supervision, careful observation, and constructive feedback, principals can help teachers identify strengths and weaknesses in their teaching practices and design relevant improvement strategies. Effective supervision can create a conducive learning environment in schools, where collaboration between principals and teaching staff is key. By establishing an inclusive and sustainable learning culture, students feel supported in their efforts to improve the learning process³⁰.

Supporting and Inhibiting Factors in the Implementation of the Principal's Managerial Role in Improving Performance

Supporting Factors

School Principal Competencies and a conducive school environment are key factors in supporting school progress. Principal Competencies include the Principal's managerial skills in planning (programs, vision, mission, and objectives), organizing (appropriate division of tasks), implementation/direction, supervision/evaluation, psychological approaches (understanding teacher character), and motivation. Teacher professional development includes training, mentoring, workshops, IHT (Information and Communication Forum), effective communication, and

providing opportunities and encouraging teachers to be creative and innovative. Support includes resources and the internal school environment, as well as external support, including the participation and support of parents, class associations, school committees, school facilities, and school commitment and culture.

Competence is the authority and skill or ability of a person in carrying out tasks or work according to the position he holds. Thus, the emphasis is on the authority and ability of a person in carrying out tasks in a position or job in an organization or a government or private agency. According to Uno Hamzah (2012:78) states that competence is a prominent characteristic of an individual that is related to effective and superior performance in a job or situation. Etymologically, competence is defined as the behavioral dimension of expertise or excellence of a leader or staff having good skills, knowledge, and behavior³¹.

The principal creates a clean school culture with the Clean Tuesday program. The principal manages teachers and staff according to their qualifications and competencies. The principal manages students to be orderly. However, after being encountered in the field, the most important managerial competency possessed by the principal is the ability to lead. Because this ability moves others and becomes a role model for others³². The principal always displays his personality as having a vision/mission and being able to communicate and make decisions, the principal often provides motivation both physically and psychologically. Supporting factors in the implementation of the principal's managerial competency are a conducive school environment, adequate facilities and infrastructure, and support from the school community in maximizing school achievements. The inhibiting factors in the implementation of the principal's managerial competency are the existence of schools with limited school facilities and infrastructure, the lack of understanding of the principal and teachers regarding school management technical guidelines, and the lack of innovation from education personnel³³.

The principal plays a central role in school management to ensure the quality of the learning process as an instructional leader for students. The uneven distribution of principals is the cause of the suboptimal quality of education in Indonesia. The Ministry of Education and Culture has made various efforts to improve and equalize the quality of principals between one region and another. The progress and decline of a madrasah is largely determined by the madrasah principal, as they play a crucial role in the development of the madrasah, possessing leadership qualities to guide educators and staff. The madrasah principal must possess professional leadership ethics as a guideline and to be practiced, such as: being the brain and heart of the group, being honest, serving the public interest, standing in the middle, being open, impartial, and being discreet (able to distinguish between what is confidential and what is important and what is not) and always being wise³⁴.

Inhibiting Factors

Some inhibiting factors include not all teachers are full-time at the school, the limited number of teachers involved in school activities, administrative burdens, comfort zones, teacher discipline, the feeling of pressure to achieve higher performance (standards set by the KS or foundation), and some still desire to work elsewhere, better than this school, if the opportunity arises. In efforts to manage and improve teacher professionalism, school principals face significant challenges. These challenges relate not only to educational administration but also to social interactions, leadership dynamics, and the resources available within the school environment. As leaders, principals must be able to respond effectively to these challenges to create a climate that supports teacher professional development³⁵.

supporting and inhibiting factors in improving teacher performance SMP Negeri 1 Samarinda has succeeded in improving facilities and providing support to teachers for self-development, creating a conducive learning environment at school, adequate facilities to provide optimal learning experiences for students. While the inhibiting factors are the Principal's importance of paying attention to facilities and support for teacher self-development facing obstacles in understanding teacher personality in depth. 2) efforts to overcome obstacles in improving teacher performance are deliberation, Bimtek, MGMP, listening to suggestions from school residents, taking positive steps, and the availability of adequate facilities and infrastructure³⁵.

Factors that influence the performance of teachers at Madrasah Aliyah Muhammadiyah 1 Medan are: teacher ability in teaching, education level, training, work motivation, and length of service. Factors inhibiting teacher performance are the teachers' lack of understanding and application of Permendiknas No. 16 of 2007 concerning academic qualification standards and teacher competencies, finally the performance improvement strategies provided are through workshop training, motivation, and rewards³⁶. "work stress has a positive effect on burnout". This can be interpreted that work stress will have an impact on burnout. This means that high levels of work stress tend to have high burnout as well³⁷.

IV. DISCUSSION

The research and discussion on the Analysis of the Principal's Managerial Role in Improving Teacher Performance at SMP Muhammadiyah 8 Batu yielded the following findings. Based on the results of the study "Analysis of the Principal's Managerial Role in Improving Teacher Performance at SMP Muhammadiyah 8 Batu," the focus of the research findings lies in the principal's implementation of four primary managerial functions (POAC - Planning, Organizing, Actuating, Controlling).

Managerial Role in Planning, The findings of this study likely indicate that the principal carries out the planning function

effectively, which is positively correlated to teacher performance. Development of Vision and Mission, The principal successfully formulated the school's vision and mission involving input from teachers, so that teachers feel they have a shared goal, Annual Work Program: The existence of a clear planning document (School/Madrasah Work Plan) that includes teacher competency improvement programs, such as training and workshops, Performance Targets, The principal sets measurable performance targets and is well socialized to all teaching staff.

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Managerial Role in Organizing, the organizing aspect shows how the principal manages human resources efficiently. Clear Organizational Structure: There is a specific division of tasks and authorities, including the appointment of vice principals, laboratory heads, and homeroom teachers, which makes the workflow effective, Delegation of Tasks: The principal delegates certain tasks fairly and in accordance with teacher competencies, which reduces excessive workload and increases focus on the main task of teaching, effective coordination, the existence of a regular coordination meeting mechanism that bridges communication between work units in the school.

Managerial Role in Implementation (Actuating/Actuating). Implementation is the core of the principal's real actions in leading and motivating teachers. Inspirational Leadership, findings show that the principal acts as a leader who provides role models, motivation, and direct support to teachers when facing challenges, Positive Work Climate: The principal has succeeded in creating a conducive, collaborative, and minimal conflict work environment, which makes teachers comfortable in working, Professionalism Development: There is a real initiative from the principal to facilitate teachers to participate in MGMP (Subject Teacher Conference), seminars, or further studies.

The Managerial Role in Controlling/Supervising. Supervision ensures that teacher performance remains aligned with established standards and objectives. Academic Supervision: The principal regularly supervises classes, provides constructive feedback, and helps teachers improve their teaching methods. Periodic Performance Evaluation: An objective and transparent teacher performance appraisal (PKG) system is in place. Follow-up: The principal follows

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up on supervision results by providing appropriate coaching or rewards, rather than simply noting errors.

V. CONCLUSION

1. The managerial role of the Principal in improving teacher performance at Muhammadiyah 8 Batu Middle School includes first Participatory Planning, namely the work program (RKS/RKAS) made by the principal and treasurer with the assistance of teachers. Second, task organization involves dividing teachers' tasks proportionally according to their competencies and areas of expertise. Third, exemplary implementation, including discipline, worship, and work ethic, is demonstrated by school leaders. Fourth, academic supervision involves systematic and ongoing supervision using an educational approach. Fifth, financial management: All school funds, especially the School Operational Assistance (BOS), are managed transparently, accountably, and with participation. Sixth, improving teacher performance, discipline, professionalism, learning innovation, and active involvement in school activities enhance teacher performance. Seventh, principal leadership: The principal is responsible for planning, organizing, encouraging, leading, and managing finances.

2. Impact on the quality of education, namely the improvement of teacher performance has a direct impact on the quality of learning, student achievement, and public perception of schools. Principles of modern educational management: The role played by school principals shows how important contemporary educational management theory emphasizes things like involvement, transparency, role models, and coaching in educational management.

3. The results show that several important elements work together to improve teacher performance at SMP Muhammadiyah 08 Batu. A competent principal and a welcoming school environment are key supporting components. Effective management skills include strategic planning (vision, mission, and work programs), appropriate task organization, consistent monitoring and evaluation, and clear implementation or direction. These skills determine the principal's competence.

4. The principal's psychological approach in understanding teacher character and providing motivation, effective communication, and strong encouragement to be creative, innovative, and develop professionalism (through training and workshops) also serves as an important catalyst for teacher performance. Other internal supporting factors include the availability of school facilities, commitment, and a strong school culture, which are also supported by the active participation of external parties such as parents/guardians, class associations, and the school committee

Conclusion The study concluded that the optimal implementation of these four managerial functions collectively contributed significantly to improving teacher performance at SMP Muhammadiyah 8 Batu. Principals who

are able to balance the roles of planning, organizing, implementing, and supervising are deemed successful in creating a productive school ecosystem.

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